

Atmospheric pressure gas chromatography coupled to quadrupole-time of flight mass spectrometry as a tool for identification of volatile migrants from autoadhesive labels used for direct food contact

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Abstract

Pressure sensitive adhesives (PSA) are used to manufacture labels that are stick directly on the food. These adhesives could contain not only intentionally added compounds to the adhesive formula but also non-intentionally added substances (NIAS), as consequence of impurities from the raw materials used, decomposition of the initial components or from chemical interactions between them. These compounds could migrate to food and contaminate it. In this study gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS/Q) and atmospheric pressure gas chromatography coupled to a quadrupole hyphenated to a time of flight mass spectrometer (APGC-MS/Q-TOF) have been used for identification of unknown compounds and NIAS coming from a PSA.

Seven compounds were identified by GC-MS/Q and other eight compounds remained initially unknown. The structure of these eight new compounds was elucidated working with the spectra obtained by APGC-MS/Q-TOF. These compounds were classified in classes III and II of Cramer toxicity. Migration studies were carried out using Tenax as solid food simulant and the results showed values for estimated dairy intake (EDI) lower than those established by Cramer in each toxicity class.

Keywords

APGC-Q-TOF, NIAS, pressure sensitive adhesives, food contact material, risk exposure

Introduction

Food packaging labels have the purpose of informing about the product and motivate the consumer to buy it. In some cases, where the product is sold without a packaging, labels are stick directly in the food with a pressure sensitive adhesive (PSA). Some examples are fruits, cured cheeses and cold meats.

Adhesives are complex mixtures that include a high variety of compounds. The main components of an adhesive are a resin, catalysts, hardeners, accelerators, inhibitors, retarders, solvents, thickeners, diluents, extenders, fillers, carriers, plasticizers, flexibilizers, tackifiers, film formers, antioxidants, antihydrolysis, antifungals, soaps, surfactants and wetting agents [1]. With the exception of resin, most of these additives have molecular weight lower than 1000 amu and consequently they could migrate from the label to the food, as they are in direct contact with it. As a result, the migration study is compulsory before launching them in the market. However, not only the intentionally added substances (IAS) but also the non intentionally added substances (NIAS) from the adhesive formula could end in the food. In adhesives formula, NIAS could appear from impurities from the raw materials used, decomposition of the initial components or because of chemical interactions between them. These compounds could also migrate and affect the food safety. Therefore, it is very important to identify them.

Identification of unknown compounds is a challenging work. Gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry in electron impact mode has been used previously for identification of volatile unknowns in adhesives for food contact [2-5]. The spectra obtained in these analyses are compared with a spectrum library and identification can be done. Nevertheless, databases are limited and identification is not always possible. Therefore, additional analyses are necessary.

Atmospheric pressure gas chromatography coupled to time of flight analyzer (APGC-MS/Q-TOF) is an interesting tool that could be very valuable in this kind of analysis. APGC is a novel analytical technique, based on APCI [6], with a plasma generated by a corona pin that supplies reagent ions to ionize the target molecules. The ionization processes are driven by a plasma formed by the interaction between nitrogen molecules and electrons. The ionization has two possible processes, charge transfer or protonation, therefore mass spectra can be dominated by M^+ , $M+H^+$ or $M-H^-$. This fact, combined with a Q-TOF analyser that provides accurate mass of the molecular ion and its fragments, as

well as with the help of chemical database, could lead to obtain an identification of compounds [7-10].

The aim of this paper is to explore the potential of the novel technique APGC-MS/Q-TOF to study the likely migrants from a complex adhesive that is going to be in contact with food.

Experimental

Materials

The adhesive selected for the study was a pressure sensitive adhesive (PSA). This adhesive is normally used for labels for direct food contact for cheese and cold meats. The adhesive was supplied by Samtack (Barcelona, Spain).

Labels for direct food contact were made with the adhesive. The labels consisted of 20 g/m² of PSA applied over 36 µm polyethylene terephthalate (PET). The labels were supplied by Samtack (Barcelona, Spain).

Rice paper of a gramage of 17 g/m² used for the migration studies was purchased from OCB (France).

The following reagents: decahydronaphthalene, 3-octanol, 1-methyl-3-methoxy-4-isopropylbenzene and tert-butyldicyclohexylphosphine were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich Química S.A (Madrid, Spain).

HPLC-MS quality methanol and ultrapurified water were supplied by J. T. Baker (Deventer, The Netherlands). Analytical grade isooctane was supplied by Scharlau Chemie S.A (Sentmenat, Spain).

Sample preparation and migration tests

Firstly, in order to identify the non-target compounds in the adhesive, solutions of the PSA were prepared. 1 g of PSA was dissolved in 100 g of isooctane. Then 1 µL of this solution was analyzed by GC-MS and APGC-Q-TOF.

In addition, 1 g of PSA was extracted with 10 g methanol. Then, 1 g of this solution was diluted in ultrapurified water. The solution was analyzed by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS).

The migration studies were prepared as follows. The labels were stuck to rice paper. As a result a laminate made with PET-PSA-rice paper was obtained. Then pieces of 2,5x5 cm of this laminate were placed in Petri dishes. The paper side of the laminate was covered with 0,5 g of Tenax, 4 g Tenax per dm² laminate in accordance with UNE-EN 14338 [11]. The same procedure was done with rice paper used as blank.

Tenax was extracted following the procedure optimized by Vera et al. [12]. The final extraction method was as follows: 0.5 g of Tenax ® was extracted two consecutive times with 1.7 mL of methanol each time. The two extracts were mixed and then the final extract was concentrated under a N₂ stream to 200 µL and analyzed by GC-MS. Three replicates of the migration assay were prepared and analyzed.

Instrumentation

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry_single quadrupole (GC-MS/Q)

The equipment used was a CTC Analytics CombiPal autosampler coupled to an Agilent 6890N gas chromatograph with a mass spectrometer MS 5975B detector. All of them from Agilent Technologies (Madrid, Spain).

The capillary column used was a HP-5MS (30 m x 0,25 µm x 250 µm) from Agilent Technologies (Madrid, Spain). The oven program was as follows: 40°C for 2 min, with rate of 10°C/min up to 300 ° C, maintained for 2 min. The injection type was splitless and the helium flow was 1ml/min. The acquisition was done in electron impact ionization (EI). The mass detector was set at SCAN mode (in the range m/z 45-350).

Atmospheric pressure gas chromatography-mass spectrometry_quadrupole-time of flight (APGC-MS/Q-TOF)

The equipment used for the chromatography was a CTC Analytics CombiPal autosampler coupled to an Agilent 6890 N de Agilent. The capillary column used was a HP-5MS (30 m x 0,25 µm x 250 µm) from Agilent Technologies (Madrid, Spain). The oven program

was as follows: 40°C for 2 min, with rate of 10°C/min up to 300 ° C, maintained for 2 min. The injection type was splitless and the helium flow was 1ml/min.

The detector was an APGC (atmospheric pressure gas chromatography) source coupled to mass spectrometer consisting of a hexapole, a cuadrupole, a collision cell and a time of flight analyzer (Q-TOF) Xevo G2 from Waters (Milford, MA, USA).

API positive polarity and sensitivity analyzer mode were selected. The mass range considered was m/z 45-450. The corona voltage was 2.1 kV, the sampling cone voltage was set at 10 V and at 30 V, the cone gas was set at 200 L/h and the source temperature was 150° C. The lockmass reference used was perfluorotributylamine.

The transfer line settings were as follows: make up gas used was nitrogen at 400 mL/min and the transfer line temperature was 350 °C.

MSE mode was selected for the acquisition; collision ramp energy from 20 to 40 V was used.

Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS)

ICP-MS measurements were carried out with a quadrupole ICP-MS instrument, Agilent 7500. This instrument was equipped with a Babington nebulizer and a double pass spray chamber.

Analysis of phosphorous (m/z 31) was done in the samples and in the blank. Full quant (3 central points per peak) was selected as peak pattern, integration time was 0.1 s, integration time/ mass was 0.3 s and the number of repetitions was 10.

Results and discussion

Identification

In this work, non-targeted analysis of the sample was done since no information about the compounds in the adhesive was available. There is not a single technique that can provide all the necessary data for the identification of these compounds. In this work, APGC-MS/Q-TOF is presented as a powerful and useful technique for the challenge of untargeted measurements.

GC-MS/Q

In the first place, the identification of the compounds in the adhesive was carried out by GC-MS/Q. The extract coming from the adhesive was analyzed following the procedures optimized in previous works related with adhesives [2, 4, 5, 12, 13]. Figure 1 shows the chromatogram obtained.

NIST 08 mass spectral search program version 2.0 was used for the identification of the compounds. NIST 08 returns a "hit list" of matched chemical compounds from the library. In this work, Reverse Match Factor (RMF) has been used for the matching. This parameter is the normalized dot product with square-root scaling of the submitted mass spectrum and the library mass spectrum, but the elements that are not present in the library mass spectrum are not included. This NIST 08 tool is especially useful when the spectrum represents more than a single compound. It can be seen in Figure 1 that there are many peaks between the retention times 18 and 21 min. In this region of the chromatogram, clean spectra of each single compound are difficult to obtain so the RMF tool was useful. Table 1 shows the list of 21 compounds detected in this work. Only 7 compounds obtained a reverse match over 800, which was considered the value that could lead to identification. These compounds were naphthalene, decahydro derivatives and isomers of octadecadienol. These compounds could come from the petroleum-based solvent used for the production of the hydrocarbon resin [14] of the PSA.

Once the GC-MS/Q analysis was done, 14 compounds still remained totally unknown. Therefore, APGC-MS/Q-TOF was used in order to try to identify the compounds.

APGC-MS/Q-TOF

Atmospheric pressure gas chromatography (APGC) is a novel analytical technique that allows a conventional GC to be coupled to an atmospheric source on a Q-TOF. The ionization processes are driven by a plasma formed by the interaction of nitrogen molecules and electrons generated by a corona pin. Mass spectra can be dominated by M^+ , $[M+H]^+$ or $[M-H]^-$ [15].

APGC can generate mass spectra dominated by the molecular ion with reduced fragmentation when the cone voltage is set relatively low (10V). This fact, combined with a TOF analyser that provides accurate mass, as well as the use of chemical database, could lead to obtain a molecular formula of the compound.

Moreover, fragmentation combined with accurate mass can provide information about the molecular structure and that could lead to the identification of the unknowns. Fragmentation with an APGC-MS/Q-TOF is possible in two different ways. In the first place, fragmentation can be generated with the cone voltage. When cone voltage is increased, controllable level of fragmentation can be induced. In the second place, fragmentation can be generated in the collision cell, increasing collision voltage.

Conditions used for the acquisition are explained before. The chromatogram was acquired in MS^E mode. MS^E mode is a method of data acquisition that involves the rapid alternation between two energy conditions, thus providing the accurate mass of the precursor ion, in addition to fragment ions, for further confirmatory purposes. As a result, two functions are obtained in a single run. Function 1, that is the low-energy function. Precursor ion spectra that can lead to a molecular formula of the compound are obtained in this function. Function 2, the high energy function, which is the result of applying a ramp of collision voltage in the collision cell. Mass fragments that can lead to structure elucidation are obtained in this function.

Figure 2 shows the chromatogram obtained by APGC-MS/Q-TOF. Peaks profile obtained were different to peak profile obtained by GC-MS/Q electron impact ionization (figure 1). These differences can be attributed to the different ionization processes that take place in each technique.

Spectra of each peak were studied in order to elucidate the compounds. In the first place, spectra coming from function 1 with both cone voltages were studied for each peak in order to obtain a molecular formula. Taking the accurate mass of the molecular ion in each spectrum, different possibilities for molecular formula were established. The criteria taken into account were a) the i-Fit, that is the probability that the isotope pattern of a particular elemental composition in the list of results matches the peaks in the measured spectrum and b) the mass tolerance, that was set at 3 mDa.

Table 1 shows that the most probable molecular formula of the compounds 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14 and 17 was C₁₅H₃₀NP. Since phosphorous is not a very common element in adhesive samples, qualitative ICP-MS analysis were carried out. The presence of phosphorous in the sample was confirmed as the sample contained an amount of phosphorous three times higher than the blank. Moreover, following the criteria mentioned above, the molecular formula of the compound number 18 was C₁₈H₂₈O₃.

Once molecular formula of each accurate mass were known, it was necessary to use a database of chemical compounds and to know the typical composition of a pressure sensitive adhesive in order to elucidate the possible compounds that could be present in the sample. For this work the databases [www.chemspider.com][16] and [www.scifinder.org][17] were used in order to obtain a list of candidates for the identification. The molecular formula C₁₅H₃₀NP, returned only one hit in the database Chemspider and 10 hits in the database Scifinder. A bibliographic search was done about if these compounds are commonly used to manufacture PSA adhesives. It was found that phosphine derivatives are used as catalyzers in resin polymerizations [18-20] Therefore, these compounds were proposed as the most likely candidates.

The molecular formula C₁₈H₂₈O₃ returns 592 hits at Chemspider and 2477 hits at Scifinder. Then, the compounds were arranged by number of references and a bibliographic search about if these compounds are used to manufacture PSA adhesives was done. Finally, it was found out that antioxidants such as Irganox are commonly used in adhesive formulations [21]. Methyl-3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)propanoate was one of the hits found in the databases and it was a fragment of the Irganox molecule. This compound was set as the main candidate for the identification.

Then, using the high energy function (function 2) fragmentation spectra were obtained. The accurate masses of the fragments were considered in order to find out if they could be generated from the candidates obtained in the databases and then confirm their identification.

The software MassFragment from Waters (Milford, MA, USA) was used in order to match each fragment obtained by APGC-MS/Q-TOF with a fragment of the candidate proposed with the databases. This software is based on chemically intelligent algorithms. It proposes ion structures coming from fragments of the candidate obtained on the databases, along with the exact mass errors and scores for each proposed structure. The scores are obtained based on the likelihood of breaking certain bonds and how well the results agree with the exact mass generated. Therefore, the lower the score and the better the mass accuracy, the higher the confidence is in obtaining the correct structure for the fragment ion interrogated.

As a result, some compounds were identified (table 1). Figure 3A shows the spectra of the function 1 obtained at a cone voltage of 30 V of the compound 1-

(dicyclohexylphosphino)-N,N-dimethylmethanamine. In this spectrum it can be observed that at this voltage, fragmentation was produced. Nevertheless, the molecular ion $[M+H]^+$, was found and it was confirmed with the spectra obtained at 10 V. Moreover, figure 3B shows the spectrum of the function 2 for this compound. It was obtained applying a cone voltage of 30 V and collision ramp energy in the collision cell from 20 to 40 V. Making a comparison of both spectra it can be seen that in figure 3A there are many ions with a high m/z because fragmentation was relatively soft. The most abundant fragment was 159.11 since its fragmentation didn't imply a ring fragmentation. In this molecule, ring fragmentations happened, involving cleavage of two bonds as saturated alicyclic hydrocarbons normally decompose [22].

In contrast, figure 3B shows that the most abundant ions in function 2 were the ones with a lower m/z , because the fragmentation was more aggressive since a collision ramp was applied.

Figure 3 shows the scores obtained for the fragments that ranged from 0.5 to 5. The value $S=0.5$ was obtained when the fragmentation implied only one bond and $S=5$ was obtained when four bonds were broken, as this case is less advantageous. On the other hand, the difference between the m/z obtained for each fragment by APGC-MS/Q-TOF and the theoretical m/z of the fragment candidates proposed ranged between 0.4 mDa and 1.4 mDa (figure 3). Therefore, they were below the mass accuracy of the Q-TOF equipment, that was set at a maximum of 3 mDa in the calibration of the instrument.

Table 1 shows that 7 isomers of this compound were identified in the sample. Figure 4 shows the chemical structure of the different isomers of the dicyclohexylphosphino derivative. The spectra of all of the seven isomers found in the adhesive, had a high abundance of m/z 159.11 that implied the fragmentation of a methyl group bonded to nitrogen. Because of that, the isomer 3-(dicyclohexylphosphino)propan-1-amine could not be present in the sample, since this molecule does not have a methyl group bonded to nitrogen. The other 7 isomers were present in the sample.

The oral toxicity of these compounds have not been studied yet, then Toxtree theoretical classification was used to estimate it based on the chemical structure (table 1). These compounds were classified in class III of Cramer toxicity, that is the highest class of toxicity according to the decision tree [23, 24]. This is very remarkable information as

the adhesive company ignored the presence of these compounds in the resin they used for the adhesive formulation.

Figure 5A shows the spectra of the function 1 obtained at 30 V of cone voltage for the compound methyl-3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)propanoate. At this voltage the molecular ion $[M+H]^+$ was the most abundant ion, as there was not fragmentation due to the presence of an aromatic nucleus that produces stabilization by charge delocalization [22].

Figure 5B shows fragmentation in function 2, where collision voltage was applied. The scores obtained for the fragments ranged from 0.5 to 12. The value $S=0.5$ was obtained when only one bond was fragmented and it did not involve the aromatic ring. The highest scores were obtained when fragmentation implied the bond between the aromatic ring and the tert-butyl group as the cleavage of this bond is more hindered. Moreover, the difference between m/z obtained for each fragment by APGC-MS/Q-TOF and the theoretical m/z of the fragment candidates proposed ranged between 0.0 mDa and 1.0 mDa (figure 5B). Therefore, they were below the mass accuracy of the Q-TOF equipment, that was set at a maximum of 3 mDa in the calibration of the instrument.

This compound is a non-intentionally added substance (NIAS) as it is a degradation product from Irganox 1076 used as antioxidant in the adhesive formulation. The oral toxicity of this compound has not been studied yet, so Toxtree theoretical classification was used in order to estimate it (table 1), as was above mentioned. This compound was classified as class II of Cramer toxicity, that is medium toxicity. Besides, this compound has a molecular weight of 292 Da. It is a semivolatile compound that will have a higher tendency to migrate than Irganox 1076 with a higher molecular weight (531 Da). The presence of this compound reaffirms the importance of identifying the compounds in a sample intended to be in direct contact with food, as this NIAS could migrate to food and contaminate it.

Migration study

Adhesives are not yet covered by a specific EU legislation. Nevertheless, they must comply Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 [25] that requires that materials and articles, must not transfer their constituents to food in quantities which could endanger human health.

As a result, in order to find out if the adhesive contaminates the food, migration studies must be done.

In general, migration studies are done using simulants proposed by the European Union [26]. The simulants selected in each case depend on the food that is going to be in contact with the material under study. In this case, the adhesive is normally used for labels for direct food contact with fatty food and the recommended simulants are vegetable oil or their substitutes, isooctane and ethanol-water 95% (w/w). However, the adhesive studied was soluble in all of them. Because of that it was decided to do migration assays with poly(2,6-diphenyl-p-phenylene oxide) (Tenax®) that is normally used in a similar case, when the material studied is paper, that deteriorated with all the solvents [11].

Since this adhesive is a PSA for labels and it was very sticky, Tenax could not be exposed directly over the labels because it could not be removed after the migration assay to be analyze. Because of that, the labels were stuck to rice paper, as this paper was considered slimmer and porous enough to let the compounds diffuse quickly through it and reach the Tenax.

Table 2 shows the migration results considering that all the packaging was covered by the adhesive. Migration of compounds ranged from 6.07 to 97.14 ng/g simulant.

In order to evaluate the risk of exposure, the estimated daily intake (EDI) established by FDA (Food and Drug Administration of United States) [27] was calculated using the following equation:

$$EDI \left(\frac{mg}{person \times day} \right) = migration \left(\frac{mg}{Kg} \right) \times 3Kg (food \text{ intake per person and day}) \times CF$$

Where CF is the fraction of the daily diet expected to be in contact with a specific packaging material (for adhesives is 0.14)

These values were compared with the maximum values recommended for human exposure (mg per person per day) that was established by Cramer for each toxicity class. The values for class I, II and III are 1.8, 0.54 and 0.09 mg per person per day respectively [28].

Table 2 shows the EDI calculated from the migration values and their toxicity classes according Cramer. All these values were below the maximum values recommended by Cramer. Moreover, the actual application of this adhesive does not cover the entire food

surface as it is used for labels to tag the food. Then, migration must be recalculated for each single case but, in all cases will be lower than the values shown in table 2. Subsequently, the labels studied here comply with Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 since migration of compounds coming from the adhesive does not endanger human health.

Conclusions

This work has established that identification of unknown compounds in a sample intended to be in contact with food is an essential step before migration studies. It has been proved that non-intentionally added substances (NIAS) that have been identified in the sample studied here, migrated to the food simulant used here for the migration assays.

APGC-MS/Q-TOF has demonstrated to be a powerful technique, supplementary to traditional GC-MS, for the identification of unknowns. The fact that provides accurate mass spectra of both molecular ion and fragments of it, combined with a huge bibliographic search and suitable software leads to the identification of several compounds present in the sample.

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Table 1. Number of the compound in the chromatogram, retention time (min), compound name and its Toxtree class, match factor of spectra obtained by GC-Q-MS, molecular formula, accurate mass measured and difference between the theoretical mass and the accurate mass expressed in mDa measured by APGC-Q-TOF.

N°	Tr (min)	Compound name (Toxtree class)	GC-Q-MS		APGC-Q-TOF	
			Match factor	Molecular formula	Accurate mass measured	Mass error (Δ mDa)
1	17.70	Unknown compound				
2	17.94	Naphthalene, decahydro-1,6-dimethyl-4-(1-methylethyl)- (I)	830			
3	17.98	Naphthalene, decahydro-2,6-dimethyl-3-octyl (I)	800			
4	18.05	4,7-dimethyl-1-isopropyl-perhydronaphthalene (I)	803			
5	18.24	Z,E-2,13-Octadecadien-1-ol (I)	810			
6	18.32	Z,Z-2,13-Octadecadien-1-ol (I)	801			
7	18.38	E,Z-2,13-Octadecadien-1-ol (I)	820			
8	18.50	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer*(III)		C15H30NP	256.2195	-0.1
9	18.60	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer*(III)		C15H30NP	256.2195	-0.1
10	18.75	Unknown compound				
11	18.90	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer*(III)		C15H30NP	256.2195	-0.1
12	19.00	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer*(III)		C15H30NP	256.2195	-0.1
13	19.11	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer*(III)		C15H30NP	256.2195	-0.1
14	19.17	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer* (III)		C15H30NP	256.2195	-0.1
15	19.41	Unknown compound				
16	19.52	Naphthalene, decahydro-1,1-dimethyl-(III)	850			
17	19.61	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer*(III)	-	C15H30NP	256.2195	-0.1
18	20.11	Methyl-3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)propanoate (II)	733	C18H28O3	292.2051	1.0
19	20.69	Unknown compound				
20	20.71	Unknown compound				
21	21.02	Unknown compound				

Table 2. Number of compound in the chromatogram, retention time, compound name, limit of detection (ng/g) , migration values (ng/g) considering that 100% of the packaging was covered by adhesive and EDI values (estimated daily intake) expressed as mg/person/day

N°	Tr (min)	Compound name	LOD (ng/g)	Migration (ng/g)	EDI (mg/person/day)
2	17.94	Naphthalene, decahydro-1,6-dimethyl-4-(1-methylethyl)- (I)	6.1	12.5	0.005
3	17.98	Naphthalene, decahydro-2,6-dimethyl-3-octyl (I)	6.1	35.57	0.015
4	18.05	4,7-dimethyl-1-isopropyl-perhydronaphthalene (I)	6.1	62.50	0.026
5	18.24	Z,E-2,13-Octadecadien-1-ol (I)	5.3	6.07	0.003
6	18.32	Z,Z-2,13-Octadecadien-1-ol (I)	5.3	30.39	0.013
7	18.38	E,Z-2,13-Octadecadien-1-ol (I)	5.3	19.83	0.008
8	18.50	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer*(III)	8.7	33.18	0.014
9	18.60	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer*(III)	8.7	29.94	0.013
10	18.75	Unknown compound		77.95	0.033
11	18.90	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer*(III)	8.7	27.43	0.012
12	19.00	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer*(III)	8.7	20.16	0.008
13	19.11	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer*(III)	8.7	16.23	0.007
14	19.17	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer* (III)		14.97	0.006
15	19.41	Unknown compound		85.43	0.036
16	19.52	Naphthalene, decahydro-1,1-dimethyl-(III)	6.1	97.14	0.041
17	19.61	Dicyclohexylphosphino isomer*(III)	8.7	34.38	0.014
18	20.11	Methyl-3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)propanoate (II)	7.2	90.86	0.038

Figure 1. Chromatogram of the isooctane extract of the adhesive sample obtained by GC-MS/Q

Figure 2. Chromatogram of the isooctane extract of the adhesive sample obtained by APGC-MS/Q-TOF

Figure 3. A) Spectrum show the spectra of the function 1 obtained at a cone voltage of 30 V of the compound 1-(dicyclohexylphosphino)-N,N-dimethylmethanamine B)spectrum of the function 2 of the compound 1-(dicyclohexylphosphino)-N,N-dimethylmethanamine

Figure 4. Chemical structure of the different isomers of the dicyclohexylphosphino derivative

Figure 5. A) Spectrum show the spectra of the function 1 obtained at a cone voltage of 30 V of the compound methyl-3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)propanoate B)spectrum of the function 2 of the compound methyl-3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)propanoate